

To Study The Variation of Scale Factor In The Homogeneous Universe with k-Essence Scalar Field

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ABSTRACT

Here, I have studied the variation between the time rate of homogeneous part of the k-essence scalar field $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ with the scale factor $a(t)$. The late time acceleration of the universe implies the change in scale factor $a(t)$. The spherically symmetric k-essence scalar field $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$ is taken here. I have obtained a relation between $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ and $a(t)$ using the solution obtained from the Lagrangian equation approximated in an FLRW universe. To plot the relation, I have taken the range of scale factor $a(t)$ to be in between 0 and 1. I have shown that the variation of $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ depends on parameters B and D . I have taken different set of values for those parameters and produced several plots between $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ and $a(t)$. The results have shown that for smaller values of D , $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ becomes independent of the scale factor $a(t)$. For negative values of B , the $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ becomes asymptotic with the increase of scale factor $a(t)$.

Keywords:

Early Universe, k-Essence Scalar Field, Scale factor, Dark energy, Accelerating universe

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Notations and Abbreviations

- $\phi(r, t)$ = Spherically symmetric k-essence scalar field
- $a(t)$ = Scale factor of the expanding universe
- $\phi_1(r)$ = Inhomogeneous part of the k-essence field
- $\phi_2(t)$ = Homogeneous part of the k-essence field
- $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ = Rate of change of homogeneous part of the k-essence field
- FLRW Metric = Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker Metric for homogeneous universe
- LTB Metric = Lemaitre-Bondi-Tolman Metric for inhomogeneous universe
- SNe Ia = Supernova type Ia

Introduction

The observation of the luminosity distance from the SNe Ia data clearly indicates that our universe is going through a phase of late time accelerated expansion. The observations from Planck Satellite, Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO), power spectrum of the matter distribution of the universe also suggests the same. In an expanding universe the scale factor is always changing, that is it is a function of time. A scale factor for our universe could be defined as the rate at which the space itself is increasing for an outside observer, in other words it is just the ratio between the actual physical distance and the comoving distance. The scale factor $a(t)$ of the universe is a very important parameter to understand the evolution of the universe. So the theoretical basis of understanding the evolution of the universe and how the expansion came into place is mainly confined in relating several theoretical models with the scale factor of the universe. Different studies suggest the Dark Energy to be the key candidate which is responsible for this late time accelerated expansion. Dark energy is a mysterious form of energy which imparts negative pressure which counters the gravitational attraction resulting in accelerated phase. Recent studies shows that 70% of the total contents of the present universe is dark energy. The form of Dark energy is still under study.

To explain the Dark Energy, there are two types of models: a) Modified matter that exerts negative pressure b) Modified Gravity models like $f(R)$ gravity. One

of the modified matter models is Quintessence model. It has a potential term dominated lagrangian i.e. the potential energy of the field drives the late time accelerated expansion. On the other hand models like Tachyon model has a kinetic term dominated lagrangian and that kinetic term gives rise to late time acceleration. These are called k-essence model. In our context the k-essence lagrangian is taken as $L = -V(\phi)F(X)$ where $X = \partial^\mu\phi\partial_\mu\phi$. Here we have assumed that $F(X)$ is more general function of kinetic energy with some complicated functional relationship.

Earlier study suggests that a lagrangian can be set up for the early universe, when the universe is flat and homogeneous, with two generalised coordinates $q = \ln a(t)$ and the k-essence scalar field $\phi(t)$ with some complicated polynomial relation between them.. Here it is assumed that the potential $V(\phi)$ is constant. The study considered the scale factor to be much smaller than today's universe but much larger than the inflationary phase. Under certain assumptions the lagrangian takes the form of a harmonic oscillator with time varying frequency. In this framework a general scaling relation is obtained viz. $XF_X^2 = Ca(t)^{-6}$. The solution of the lagrangian gives a growing solution of the scale factor which indicates the expanding universe. The cosmological temperature T is inversely proportional to the scale factor. Using this the calculation of the quantum fluctuations of q gives the probability amplitude of fluctuations in the temperature present in the background radiation of the universe. This study also accounts for the chaotic inflation though this model did not take account the inflationary period.

In an another study, the lagrangian is set up using the homogeneous scalar field $\phi(t)$ in FLRW universe that is in a flat homogeneous universe. From the observed data of SNe Ia and Hubble telescope, the scale factors of several epochs have been calculated. Then it is plugged into the quantum amplitudes calculated from the fluctuations in $q(a(t))$. It gives certain results as a) The observed variation of rate

of change of scale factor b) The observed epoch when the universe went from a decelerating phase to accelerated phase of expansion. The results from the Planck Probe shows the inhomogeneities present in the CMBR is non-gaussian. To account that inhomogeneity, the scalar field is made homogeneous by introducing a small perturbation in it, viz. $\phi(t, x) = \phi(t)(1 + f)$, where f is a small inhomogeneity parameter. It is shown that the presence of inhomogeneity can affect the value of the epoch when this transition has occurred. The value of inhomogeneity parameter must be a bit negative to match the observations.

A recent study has done where the inhomogeneity is taken into account more profoundly where the scalar field itself taken to be inhomogeneous $\phi(r, t)$. The inhomogeneous metric is nothing but the perturbations from FLRW metric. One such kind of spherically symmetric, inhomogeneous metric is LTB metric. If the scalar field can be assumed to be decomposed as $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$, it leads to a scaling relation for the inhomogeneous scalar fields, $XF_X^2 = CT^{-4}$. Under certain assumptions the LTB metric could be reduced to FLRW metric, and the scaling relation is then become the scaling relation obtained for a homogeneous scalar field. In this scenario the FLRW metric could be written in terms of the dark energy field ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 . It clearly indicates that the k-essence field or the dark energy field has a key role to determining the value of the metric which in turns determines the geometry of the universe itself. It is one of the most important result that can be drawn from the models of this kind.

In my study, I have obtained the relation between the scale factor $a(t)$ and the time derivative of homogeneous part of the scalar field $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$. The relation is then plotted in several graphs for different values of constants present in that relation. The goal of this study is to understand how the time derivative of $\phi_2(t)$ is evolving with scale factor $a(t)$. During my work I am restricted to the homogeneous universe only. The values of the $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ are tabulated for different values of $a(t)$.

Methodology

2.0.1 Background

For an Inhomogeneous universe one can use the metric as Lemaitre-Bondi-Tolman metric given by

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + Y'^2 + Y^2[d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2]$$

Constructing the k-essence lagrangian and using the LTB metric a scaling relation could be introduced as $XF_X^2 = CT^{-4}$, where, it is taken that $Y(r, t) = f^{2/3}(r, t)$ and $f(r, t) = R(r)T(t)$.

The k-essence field is taken as $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$. Now solving the Euler-Lagrange Equations following relations are found:-

$$\phi_1(r) = \sqrt{2B}r \tag{2.1}$$

$$\phi_2(t) = -\frac{\sqrt{2B}}{8\alpha}(1 + 4\alpha t) \tag{2.2}$$

$$T(t) = \frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}t^{1/4}} \tag{2.3}$$

Here, B , D and α are constants and $\alpha \ll 1$

Under the limit of $Y(t, r) \rightarrow a(t)r$ the LTB metric reduces to FLRW metric i.e.

inhomogeneous universe reduces to homogeneous universe.

Using this limit and FLRW metric, it can be shown that

$$a(t) = T^{\frac{2}{3}} = \left[\frac{\dot{\phi}_2^2 D^2}{2\dot{\phi}_2^2 - 4B} \right]^{\frac{1}{6}} \quad (2.4)$$

The scaling relation is also reduced to $XF_X^2 = Ca^{-6}(t)$. In that case FLRW metric can be written as,

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - \left[\frac{\dot{\phi}_2^2 D^2}{2\dot{\phi}_2^2 - 4B} \right]^{\frac{1}{6}} 2B[d\phi_1^2 + \phi_1^2 d\theta^2 + \phi_1^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2] \quad (2.5)$$

Thus, the FLRW metric can be completely written in terms of Dark energy field ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 .

2.0.2 Theoretical Method

At first we have derived the relation between $\dot{\phi}_2$ and $a(t)$. This is done by changing the subject of the function in eq. [2.4]

$$a^6(t) = \frac{\dot{\phi}_2^2 D^2}{2\dot{\phi}_2^2 - 4B} \quad (2.6)$$

Or,

$$\dot{\phi}_2^2 = \frac{4a^6 B}{2a^6 - D^2} \quad (2.7)$$

Thus,

$$\dot{\phi}_2 = \pm \frac{2a^3 \sqrt{B}}{\sqrt{2a^6 - D^2}} \quad (2.8)$$

Using this relation we have plotted the graph $\dot{\phi}_2$ vs $a(t)$. We have taken different combinations for values of B and D.

Results

3.0.1 $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ vs. $a(t)$ Plot

Here we have shown the plots using different combinations for values of B and D viz. a) both equal b) both unequal c) B is negative and D is positive d) both fractional e) one is fraction and another is integer. Different plots are shown in the following sections.

Figure 3.1: B=0.1, D=0.1

Figure 3.2: $B=2$, $D=0.001$

Figure 3.3: $B=0.7$, $D=0.2$

Figure 3.4: $B=2$, $D=1$

Figure 3.5: $B=-0.1, D=0.005$

Figure 3.6: $B=-0.7, D=-0.6$

Figure 3.7: $B=-0.7, D=3$

Figure 3.8: B=-3, D=6

Figure 3.9: B=-5, D=2

3.0.2 Tables

The data sets from some of the above graphs are presented here.

$a(t)$	$\dot{\varphi}_2(t)$
0.40	1.89
0.44	0.73
0.48	0.60
0.52	0.51
0.56	0.47
0.60	0.46
0.64	0.46
0.68	0.45
0.72	0.45
0.76	0.44
0.80	0.44
0.84	0.44
0.88	0.44
0.92	0.44
0.96	0.44
1.00	0.44

Table 3.1: Data sets for B=D=0.1.

$a(t)$	$\dot{\varphi}_2(t)$
0.08	7.48
0.09	5.02
0.10	2.50
0.16	2.02
0.20	1.92
0.24	1.92
0.28	1.92
0.32	1.92
0.36	1.92
0.40	1.92
0.44	1.92
0.48	1.92
0.52	1.92
0.56	1.92
0.60	1.92
0.64	1.92
....

Table 3.2: Data sets for B=2, D=0.001.

$a(t)$	$\dot{\varphi}_2(t)$
0.52	5.19
0.56	1.99
0.60	1.55
0.64	1.41
0.68	1.33
0.72	1.27
0.76	1.25
0.80	1.22
0.84	1.22
0.88	1.22
0.92	1.19
0.96	1.19
1.00	1.19

Table 3.3: Data sets for B=0.7, D=0.2.

$a(t)$	$\dot{\varphi}_2(t)$
0.92	4.64
0.96	3.31
1.00	2.91

Table 3.4: Data sets for B=2, D=1.

$a(t)$	$\dot{\varphi}_2(t)$
0.04	0.00
0.08	0.00
0.12	0.00
0.16	0.00
0.20	0.02
0.24	0.04
0.28	0.06
0.32	0.09
0.36	0.13
0.40	0.17
0.44	0.24
0.48	0.32
0.52	0.41
0.56	0.54
0.60	0.70
0.64	0.94
0.68	1.32

Table 3.5: Data sets for B=-0.7, D=-0.6.

$a(t)$	$\dot{\varphi}_2(t)$
0.04	0.00
0.08	0.00
0.12	0.00
0.16	0.00
0.20	0.00
0.24	0.01
0.28	0.01
0.32	0.017
0.36	0.02
0.40	0.03
0.44	0.04
0.48	0.06
0.52	0.08
0.56	0.10
0.60	0.12
0.64	0.15
0.68	0.17
0.72	0.21
0.76	0.25
0.80	0.29
0.84	0.34
0.88	0.40
0.92	0.45
0.96	0.51
1.00	0.59

Table 3.6: Data sets for B=-3, D=-6.

Discussions

Now, from the calculations and plots from the above, I will discuss the various outcomes of this study.

- From the equation (2.7), it is clear that if we made the parameter D very small, then it can be neglected from the expression. The equation then gives constant value for $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$. Then the term $\phi_2(t)$ becomes directly proportional to time. This proportionality indicates that as the time increases more we have homogeneous dark energy field. Different observations suggest that today's universe mostly contains the homogeneous dark energy. The above situation is also true for the larger values of scale factor $a(t)$. This is evident from the Fig.3.1 to Fig. 3.4 .
- For larger values of D , it is evident from the equation (2.7) that the a^6 term in the denominator could be neglected and $\dot{\phi}_2(t) \propto a^3$ and thus it will not be constant rather it will vary more rapidly.
- If $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ is constant then the FLRW metric written in the equation (2.5) becomes only dependent on the inhomogeneous dark energy field ϕ_1 . This implies that for larger values of $a(t)$ or smaller values of D , the metric is

determined by the inhomogeneous field alone. So, as in the earlier epochs, the value of scale factor is much much smaller. It clearly indicates the earlier inhomogeneities have an impact to give the universe its present shape.

- From the plots Fig. 3.5 to Fig. 3.9, it is evident that for the negative values of B , $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ is increasing with the scale factor. This indicates that as the universe is expanding the time rate of change of homogeneous dark energy field $\phi_2(t)$ increases further and further and certainly it becomes asymptotic for a particular value of $a(t)$.
- For negative values of B , the plot shows that there is a certain increase of $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ at some particular value of scale factor $a(t)$. This can also be seen from tables. This might be the indication that there is certain changes happened at that epoch. Further investigations required to justify this claim.

Conclusion

A lagrangian is set up for inhomogeneous k-essence scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ and a spherically symmetric inhomogeneous LTB metric is used here. The lagrangian is solved under the assumption that $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$. The solution of the lagrangian gives the values of $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$ for inhomogeneous universe. Then it is shown that under some certain assumptions the LTB metric is reduced to flat FLRW metric for homogeneous universe. The FLRW metric is written completely in terms of dark energy scalar field $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$. A relation between scale factor $a(t)$ and $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ is established under this assumption. Then the subject of this expression is changed and $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ is expressed as a function of $a(t)$. Then, $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ is plotted against $a(t)$ using various values of constants B and D viz. a) both equal b) both unequal c) B is negative and D is positive d) both fractional e) one is fraction and another is integer. The data from the plots are then extracted and tabulated in a formal manner. This gives the value of $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ at different epochs of the universe for a particular value of B and D .

The study has found that by incorporation of the dark energy scalar fields in the FLRW metric that means the geometry of the space-time is determined by the dark energy field itself. Again the expression between $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ and $a(t)$ shows that for smaller values of D , the time derivative of $\phi_2(t)$ becomes constant, indepen-

dent of $a(t)$. So, the $\phi_2(t)$ becomes linear function of time. This is also true for larger values of $a(t)$, which similarly suggests that as the universe expands the scale factor becomes larger and the homogeneous dark energy field also attains higher values. For larger values of D , the $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ varies with a^3 which infers that the rate of change increase of $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ with the expansion of the universe. Both scenarios suggest that the homogeneous dark energy field must increase with the expansion of the universe. For negative values of B , the plot shows that there is a certain increase in $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ at some particular epoch. The value of the epoch depends on the constants B and D .

This work suggests that a k-essence scalar field models of this type are extremely successful to explain some of the well observed cosmological phenomena. A single scalar field is sufficient to take account for dark energy as well as to explain the late time accelerated expansion of the universe. In my study, the specific values of $a(t)$ from the current observations of JWST could improve the value of $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ more. My study shows that how the homogeneous part of the dark energy field is related to the scale factor $a(t)$ i.e. to the expansion of the universe itself. This inter relation suggests that there might a deeper connection between this type of scalar fields and the accelerated expansion of the universe. Though further study requires, this work has qualitatively proven the fact that the universe today contains the homogeneous dark energy field. The values of the parameters B and D could be found if the observed data is plugged into it. The value of $\phi_2(t)$ can be expressed in terms of $a(t)$, which will infers the actual relationships between the homogeneous field and the scale factor. Moreover, the inclusion of inhomogeneity into this work would definitely fine tune the study and predicts some of the observations more precisely. These are the future scopes of this study.

Appendices

Approximations of $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$

The relation between the $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ and the scale factor $a(t)$ is given by

$$\dot{\phi}_2 = \pm \frac{2a^3\sqrt{B}}{\sqrt{2a^6 - D^2}} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

For $D \ll a(t)$,

$$\dot{\phi}_2 = \pm \frac{2a^3\sqrt{B}}{\sqrt{2a^6}} = \pm \frac{2a^3\sqrt{B}}{\sqrt{2}a^3} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Thus, it can be easily shown that,

$$\dot{\phi}_2(t) = \text{Constant} = C \Rightarrow \phi_2(t) = Ct \quad (\text{A.3})$$

So, from the above, $\phi_2(t) \propto t$.

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